

**ORGANIZATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC COOPERATION AND
TRAINING IN THE EASTERN REGION****Akhmedov Qaxramon****Annotation**

In the article, the issues brought by Uzbekistan within the framework of the executive policy and the need for mature, quality personnel, which is felt by society, are growing. It is as a basis that the implementation of education and training in harmony in the Uzbek talim system is cited in the views of Eastern thinkers. Beyond that, socialization is evaluated as an infinite process, not limited to any age period, but rather the fact that it is a continuous process associated with the assimilation of social skills throughout the individual's life. It was mentioned by Individ that his special emphasis on the assimilation of social roles and norms of etiquette is a case in which the socialization worker is seen as an integral feature of the transmission of social experience to another individual. It can be seen from this that the socialization of the individual is not only a global issue of the present time, but also covered separately in the works of Eastern thinkers who lived several centuries ago.

Keywords: education, experience, upbringing, social experience, education, moral qualities, social relationships, friendship, harmony, socialization, knowledge giving, social justice, personality, virtue, need.

The social work profession serves the needy population in society as a service sector. So if we look at historical periods even in those times, the need to provide assistance to the disadvantaged population was considered urgent. In this regard, our grandfathers expressed in their works on improving the quality of life of the population, educating the growing younger generation and spiritual moral perfection in society. In our country, the growing relevance of the profession in recent years is known to all of us, that is, it is associated with the further improvement of the system of social services designed to help and support various categories of people.

The fourth direction of the “Development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” developed by the initiatives of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, is the priority direction of

maintaining a fair social policy, developing human capital, and includes a number of tasks. Including:

1. Consistent increase in population employment and Real income;
2. Improving the social protection and health system of the population, increasing the socio-political activity of women;
3. Implementation of targeted programs for the construction of affordable housing;
4. Development of the field of education and science;
5. Are improvements in public policy regarding youth. [1]

Personality is a separate individ, essentially a holistic socio-moral world. He embodies in himself the essence of man, his value as a being. The individual is interpreted differently in the social Humanities in terms of their orientation, research object and purpose. As an extremely complex contradictory, contradictory, self-denying being, biological, physiological, social, spiritual, spiritual, spiritual-moral and aesthetic intelligence can become a source of research in terms of the logic of life as an object of thought.

The factors of personality formation are numerous and diverse. For example, genetic, (genealogical), biological-natural, cultural, social life experience, relationship with one's own peers, etc. the genetic trait of an individual is determined by the basis of his lineage, the physiognomy reached from his ancestors, by temperament, and the biophysiological trait is determined by gaining strength to live.

Socialization of personality - the improvement of human psychological functions under the influence of educational upbringing, the assimilation of socio-moral values, norms and rules of behavior, the process and result of enrichment of the worldview.

The process of socialization has its own qualities and characteristics, is complex in composition, laws, factors, conditions, management and manifestation in a socialized person. For this reason, it reflects in itself the diverse cultural, moral, legal, labor, psychological manifestations of socialization, which are considered by various disciplines.

There are the following general mechanisms of socialization; traditional - the involvement of students in social activity through the family and intimate environment, the

creation of optimal conditions in activity and communication. Creation of necessary conditions and opportunities for the development of students by institutional – social institutions and educational institutions. Interpersonal-the involvement of students in the system of social relations, the development of communicative skills in them;

Reflexive-progressive individual awareness through pedagogical support of self-awareness, self-happiness, self-design.

The Thinker and statesman Yusuf Khos Khojib also revealed the essence in his work “Qutadg’u bilik” through 4 images on the issue of socialization;

The first is justice, he is depicted in the image of the Podshox Kuntug’di, the second is the state, minister Oyto’ldi, the third is the mind, the minister’s son is O’gdilmish, and the fourth is contented, disguised as his relative O’zgirmish.

In the process of economic socialization of an individual, the issue of Economic Education also has an important place. In this, the great thinker and statesman Nizamiddin Mir Alisher (1441-1501) Alisher Navoi. the views are of particular importance. Alloma’s views on the socialization of the individual are largely embedded in the poetic devotional “Xazoyin ulmaoniy”.

Abu Nasr Forabi’s works, such as “Fozil odmalar shahri”, “On the attainment of happiness”, “Ixso al-ulum”, “The origin of the sciences”, “On the meanings of reason”, expressed the socio-educational views of alloma. In his pedagogical views, the following can be considered.[2] We know that Farobius was the first to define education and upbringing. He believes that beautiful qualities in a person are formed by two ways – education and upbringing. Education combines theoretical qualities, while upbringing combines innate qualities – theoretical knowledge and practical vocational, behavioral qualities, says that education is carried out with speech and learning, and upbringing is carried out with practical work, experience. The combination of each shows maturity, but it shows that maturity arises depending on the extent to which knowledge and practical skills are learned.

Education is carried out in two ways: satisfactory, inspiring words and coercion. Let anyone say knowledge and wisdom, start it at an early age, overcome its word, keep it safe from evil deeds, be it away from betrayal, intrigue and cunning, be it religious, and spare not the world of knowledge and wealth from the people of knowledge. When a person has not received a good

upbringing and has not gained a good experience in marriage, he ignores many things and is disgusted with them. Such things claim that what seems inappropriate to him turns out to be necessary, that the development of spiritual moral qualities in each person in his works is the most pressing issue for each period.

“By virtue of morality, one understands qualities such as erudition, wisdom, and contemplation, conscientiousness, humility, elevation of the majority interest, truth, pursuit of spiritual elevation, fairness. But the main thing of these qualities is that each person is educated, enlightened. That is why Farobius views the concept of morality as a morality based on thought, inextricably linked with reason”.[3]

Indeed, Abu Nasr is a scientist who made a significant contribution to the development of the science of the Faroese medieval period, the Faroese carried out scientific work in all areas of Natural, Scientific and social knowledge. Farobius left behind a very rich scientific legacy. He created works in various fields of philosophy, music, philology and other natural, scientific knowledge. For a person to achieve happiness, he says, he must be the leader of a team that can make them happy. He is the governor who governs the city of Fozil from nature:

1-being healthy and not having any difficulty in completing his mission;

2-delicate in nature, savvy;

3-robust memory,

4-mental acute,

5-speaker who can explain his opinion,

6-knowledge-enthusiastic about enlightenment,

7-when eating food, drinking, being close to women, it is not hungry, but rather to be able to tiya himself (from gambling or other games) to be away from pleasure, enjoyment,

8-who loves truth and truth, righteous and truthful people, who hate lies and liars,

9-to be aware of one's worth and attentive,

10-the mole who does not chase after the world,

11th Justice,

12-notes the importance of being persistent, patient, courageous, brave.

Farobius wants to see these qualities in every mature person. In his Phosyl community, phorobius divides people into groups according to different characters. In this he says that it is necessary to pay attention to the natural characteristics, abilities, mental abilities, cognitive skills of people, not depending on their religious background, nationality, race. In his “Treatise on the paths to happiness”, he writes that “The mission of the state is to lead people to happiness. He, which he gains with the help of Science and good morals”. The Faroese state should be governed by a mature person; that is, the one who manages the community says that he must be fair, wise, comply with the laws and be able to create laws, anticipate the future, be caring for others.[4]

In the views of Abu Rayhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad Beruniy (973-1048), who is considered the star of the East, he reflected in the essence of the process of economic socialization, in the inextricable connection of social relations, material extents, interests, interests, requirements and goals of the way people live.

In Abu Rayhon Beruni's “Mineralogy”, “Geodesy”, “India”, “Relics from ancient peoples”, “Saydana”, he views Man as the Supreme perfection of nature. He divides all moral qualities of a person in his spiritual form into two types, good and evil. Three things play an important role in human maturation according to berunius ' teaching:

1. Heredity.
2. Environment.
3. Upbringing.

Beruni’s thoughts on ways, methods of acquiring scientific knowledge are also relevant for the current period. He is in teaching the reader:

- not boring the reader;
- not teaching the same thing or the same subject in knowledge;
- continuity, consistency;
- focus on interesting, mainly visual exposition of new topics, etc.

justifies the need to give.

He sees that the main reason for all vices is in ignorance. In the possession of the sciences, however, aspiration and interest in the individual highlight the environment. Beruni believes that morality should be the most basic quality of a person. This trait is not composed at once. It is composed in the process of interaction of people, social environment – the development of society.

Abu Raihan Beruni also defines moral education as follows. Morality is manifested and composed as a result of the struggle between good and evil, he says. Good and evil are used as criteria that determine a person's behavior. He introduces good qualities such as correctness, righteousness, restraint, integrity, humility, grace, steadfastness, prudence, generosity, sweet suchness, fairness in leadership, entrepreneurship. And evil vices include jealousy, misery, unhealthy competition, self-interest, officialdom, etc. Berunius uses pride in the sense of good manners, saying in "monuments" that "pride is to go before good manners and high verbs in reality, to acquire knowledge and wisdom, and to purify as much of the available impurity as possible. Whoever finds these qualities, the judgment is in his favor, and whoever lacks these, the judgment is to his detriment".[5]

Thus, Berunius divides all moral qualities in the spiritual image of man into two types, good and evil. It is in accordance with this tradition that moral concepts are important aspects of moral perfection, just as the "Red Thread" took place in the development of pedagogical thought created by mankind. Beruniy sahovat (mutual assistance, cooperation to benefit each other), muruvat (benevolence to people, honesty and truthfulness, to see the day with his own labor v.b.)as qualities that indicate the moral maturation of a person. The problem of moral maturation of a person has been a central issue in the entire educational system. Abu Rayhon beruniy condemns defects such as stinginess, falsehood, hypocrisy, manmanic arrogance that prevent him from wishing well, considers it the most severe for a person to indulge in wealth and taste, anger and ignorance.

After all, he himself left a huge spiritual legacy to future generations, proving that he himself has qualities inherent in a real perfect person, his life and creative work, his writings.

Abu Ali al Husayin ibn Abdullah ibn Khasan ibn Ali (980-1037), the great qabusian scholar who made a tremendous contribution to the development of World Science, Ibn Sina, in his great work "the laws of Tib", refers to economic upbringing; if the head of the family, says Ibn Sina, is inexperienced and unskilled, he will not be able to raise family members well, and as

a consequence will be bad results in He believes that the family will be happy if the head of the family socializes a family in a state that is sufficiently socialized and has certain experience in this regard.

Abu Ali ibn Sina, in his works “Ta’zur al-manozil”, “ laws of Tib”, “treatise on morality”, “treatise on duty”, “Al-law”, “treatise on work”, “Khai ibn-Yaqzon”, “wisdom” and others, promotes the development of spiritual moral qualities from a young age.[6] Ibn Sina believes that human behavior has some kind of impairment. These include deception, jealousy, enmity, humiliation, willlessness. It shows the need to educate children in community at school in learning and emphasizes the need to adhere to the following in education:

- 1) not keeping a book busy at once when giving knowledge to a child;
- 2) to give light to hard ori shorkali knowledge in education;
- 3) exercise to be appropriate for the age of children;
- 4) focus on teaching in school as a team in teaching;
- 5) taking into account the inclinations, interests and abilities of children when giving knowledge;
- 6) taking training with the addition of exercise.

Ibn Sina also considers that a learned friend plays an important role in the formation of high moral qualities. This is how the scientist describes friendship:

- friendship that does not leave its friend alone in danger despite any difficulties;
- similar and ideologically close friendship in interests;
- friendship aimed at satisfying one’s own self-interest and need. Ibn Sina acknowledges the first and second kind of friendship as true friendship.

One of the great services of thinkers is that they glorify the work, ability, intelligence of a person, believe in the power in it, tirelessly promote the need for human thought to be honored.

By studying the pedagogical works of the thinkers above, it can be concluded that the study of their views on the importance of education in human maturation not only in the content of socio-philosophical thoughts, but also through the sciences, which in their independent

brochures express moral issues in deep scientific and practical terms, promote education in the field of Science, the study

In place of the conclusion, we can say that socialization, being assessed as an endless process, is not limited to any age period, but, on the contrary, is a continuous process associated with the assimilation of social skills during the life of an individual. The special emphasis on the assimilation by Individ of social roles and norms of etiquette lies in the fact that the socialization worker is considered an integral feature of the transmission of social experience to another individual. From this it can be seen that the socialization of the personality has not only become a global issue of the present time, but has also been one of the topics covered separately in the works of Eastern thinkers who lived several centuries ago.

List of literatures

1. 2022-2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi 28.01.2022 yildagi PF-60-son IV Adolatli ijtimoiy siyosat yuritish, inson kapitalini rivojlantirish bandi.
2. K. Hashimov, S.Nishonova. Pedagogika tarixi. - Toshkent.:2005.- 81-b
3. K. Hashimov, S.Nishonova. Pedagogika tarixi. - Toshkent.:2005.- 82-b
4. Abu Nasr Forobiy. Fozil odamlar shahri. - Toshkent.: "Xalq merosi", 1993.-160 b
5. Abu Rayxon Beruniy. Tanlangan asarlar. 1 t. - Toshkent, 1968, 151-bet
6. K.Hoshimov, S.Nishonova, M.Inomova, R.Hasanov. Pedagogika tarixi. Toshkent.: "O'qituvchi" 1996.- 89 b.